

AN EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SOCIAL STUDIES INSTRUCTION IN ENHANCING POLITICAL AWARENESS AMONG JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN BIU LGA, BORNO STATE

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Abstract: *This study evaluates the effectiveness of Social Studies instruction in fostering political awareness among junior secondary school students in Biu Local Government Area (LGA), Borno State, Nigeria. The objectives of the study are to examine the degree to which Social Studies enhances students' political awareness, assess their understanding of political concepts, identify teaching methods employed, and evaluate the challenges affecting instruction. A descriptive survey design was employed to gather comprehensive data without altering any variables. The study population comprised all junior secondary school (JSS 1-3) students and Social Studies teachers across public and private schools in Biu LGA. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select 150 students and 90 teachers, ensuring balanced representation based on gender, class level, and school type. Data was collected through structured questionnaires tailored separately for students and teachers. These instruments covered demographic information, understanding of political concepts, instructional methods, and challenges faced in delivering content. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, mean scores) and inferential statistics (Chi-square and t-tests) via SPSS software at a 0.05 level of significance. The study anticipates revealing how effectively Social Studies instruction shapes political understanding and participation, as well as identifying critical instructional and contextual challenges in politically unstable environments.*

Introduction

Social Studies is an essential component of the Nigerian Basic Education Curriculum, designed to equip students with the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values necessary for effective participation in society (Federal Ministry of

Education, 2013). As an interdisciplinary subject, it integrates elements of history, geography, government, economics, and civic education to help learners understand and contribute meaningfully to their environment and nation. Among its core objectives is the

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development of political awareness, which involves educating students about governance, democratic values, political institutions, leadership, civic responsibilities, and the rule of law (Adeyemi, 2012).

In the context of Nigeria's democratic system, it is critical that citizens, especially young people, are politically informed and active. The junior secondary school level presents a foundational stage for introducing learners to these political concepts. Through Social Studies instruction, students are expected to gain an understanding of their rights and duties as citizens, appreciate the functions of government, and become aware of how political decisions impact their lives (Nwankwo, 2017). This political orientation is intended to prepare them for future participation in democratic processes such as voting, policy advocacy, and public discourse.

However, concerns have been raised regarding the extent to which Social Studies instruction in Nigerian schools achieves these political education objectives. Factors such as inadequate teaching methods, poorly trained teachers, lack of instructional materials, and limited classroom engagement may hinder the effectiveness of Social Studies in promoting political awareness (Ogunode & Abubakar, 2020). These challenges are especially significant in politically sensitive and educationally under-resourced areas like Biu Local Government Area in Borno State, where political instability and insecurity have long affected educational outcomes (UNESCO, 2021). Given this background, it is necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of Social Studies instruction in enhancing political awareness among junior secondary school students in Biu LGA. This

study will investigate whether the intended goals of the Social Studies curriculum are being met and explore how well students understand political concepts, the methods used in teaching them, and the challenges faced in the process. The findings of this study will be relevant for teachers, curriculum planners, policymakers, and other stakeholders interested in strengthening democratic education in Nigeria.

Problem of the Statement

Social Studies, as part of the Nigerian Junior Secondary School curriculum, is designed to develop students' understanding of their society, with one of its major goals being the promotion of political awareness and civic responsibility. In theory, the subject is expected to introduce students to key political concepts such as democracy, leadership, rule of law, electoral processes, and the rights and responsibilities of citizens (Federal Ministry of Education, 2013). However, there is growing concern that many junior secondary school students in Nigeria and particularly in Biu Local Government Area of Borno State demonstrate limited understanding of these political concepts and lack interest in political participation.

This disconnect may be attributed to various factors, such as ineffective teaching methods, limited instructional materials, lack of teacher training, and the broader challenges of insecurity and poor educational infrastructure in the region (Ogunode & Abubakar, 2020; UNESCO, 2021). Despite efforts to improve civic and political education through Social Studies, the actual impact of classroom instruction on students' political awareness remains unclear, especially in conflict-affected areas where political

instability and insecurity may weaken the education system's delivery capacity.

Given the importance of nurturing politically aware and responsible citizens from an early age, it is essential to evaluate the effectiveness of Social Studies instruction in achieving this objective. Without such an evaluation, there is a risk that a generation of students may pass through the school system without acquiring the knowledge and values necessary for meaningful participation in the democratic process. This study, therefore, seeks to examine the extent to which Social Studies instruction enhances political awareness among junior secondary school students in Biu Local Government Area, Borno State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of Social Studies instruction in enhancing political awareness among junior secondary school students in Biu Local Government Area, Borno State.

The specific objectives are:

- i. Examine the extent to which Social Studies instruction enhances political awareness among junior secondary school students in Biu LGA.
- ii. Assess the level of students' understanding of political concepts taught through Social Studies.
- iii. Identify the teaching methods employed in delivering political content in Social Studies classes.
- iv. Evaluate the challenges affecting the effectiveness of Social Studies instruction in promoting political awareness.

Literature Review

Social Studies in Nigeria are defined as an interdisciplinary subject aimed at developing responsible citizens with critical thinking skills and global awareness (Muhammad & Gaya, 2025). It focuses on human development, both physical and social, and how socio-physical activities influence decision-making processes (Abdullahi et al., 2021). The subject is crucial for inculcating knowledge, skills, and desirable attitudes valued by society (Abdullahi et al., 2021; Oluwagbohunmi, 2013). Social Studies education in Nigeria emphasizes character development, positive values, and civic competence (Oluwagbohunmi, 2013; Muhammad & Gaya, 2025). It is considered a vital tool for building human capacity and contributing to sustainable development (Bawuro et al., 2025). However, challenges such as shortage of instructional materials and the need for curriculum modernization persist (Bawuro et al., 2025; Muhammad & Gaya, 2025). Recommendations include prioritizing Social Studies at all educational levels, integrating digital tools, and providing continuous professional development for teachers (Oluwagbohunmi, 2013; Muhammad & Gaya, 2025).

Political awareness in Nigeria faces challenges, with low levels of awareness impacting citizens' capacity to make informed political choices. The mass media's role in increasing political awareness is hindered by various obstacles, necessitating full democratization of media (Ibagere, 2013). However, social studies education in secondary schools shows promise in balancing citizenship and political participation among youth across Nigeria's geopolitical zones

(Abonu, 2014). In the digital era, social media has emerged as a significant driver of political awareness and community engagement, particularly among Nigerian youth (Inobemhe, 2025). Additionally, community radio, though not yet implemented in Nigeria, holds potential for enhancing political awareness at the grassroots level through effective programming and interactive approaches (Kombol, 2014). These studies collectively emphasize the importance of diverse media channels and educational initiatives in fostering political awareness and civic engagement in Nigeria.

Research on social studies instruction in Nigeria highlights the importance of diverse teaching methods. Traditional lecture-based approaches are often less effective than innovative, student-centered techniques. Methods that promote active participation, such as guided discovery, storytelling, and inquiry, have been shown to improve student achievement (Ekiugbo, 2024; Ogene & Nnamani, 2015). Other recommended approaches include collaborative learning, internet technology, and field trips (Okafor et al., 2020). The choice of method should consider class size, lesson objectives, and the goal of developing civic competence and critical thinking skills (G. Joseph et al., 2019). While students prefer interactive methods, many teachers still rely heavily on conventional note-taking approaches. To address this, researchers suggest organizing workshops for teachers on the importance of varied instructional methods in achieving social studies objectives (Ogene & Nnamani, 2015; Ekiugbo, 2024).

Civic education theory encompasses various approaches to preparing citizens for democratic

participation. Boyte (2003) contrasts traditional "civics" focused on formal political processes with "service" learning, arguing for a populist approach emphasizing public work and democratic organizing. Henry (2024) advocates for promoting a normative vision of good citizenship to combat extremism and preserve democracy. Hanson & Howe (2011) argue that deliberative democratic theory provides a superior foundation for civic education compared to aggregative democracy, as it better addresses moral and epistemological demands while accommodating diverse viewpoints. Ahrari et al. (2016) propose a network-based approach to citizenship education in higher education, emphasizing horizontal networks among students for facilitating change, transferring civic knowledge, reinforcing norms, and enhancing learning. These diverse perspectives highlight the ongoing debate about the most effective methods for cultivating civic virtues and preparing citizens for active participation in democratic societies.

Social studies education plays a crucial role in promoting political awareness and civic engagement in Nigeria. Research indicates that social studies effectively enhance students' political knowledge, attitudes, and skills across different geopolitical zones (Abonu, 2014). It also contributes to the attainment of political ethics when integrated with civic education (Dania, 2015). Teachers perceive social studies as an instrument for fostering peaceful coexistence by promoting tolerance and civic responsibility (Omiyefa, 2024). Furthermore, social studies education is recognized as essential for achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development

Goals in Nigeria by creating awareness and encouraging active participation in addressing societal challenges (Suleman, 2023). These studies collectively emphasize the importance of social studies in developing informed and engaged citizens. However, some research suggests that there may be differences in perceptions based on factors such as gender, location, and school type (Dania, 2015; Omiyefa, 2024), indicating the need for a nuanced approach to social studies education implementation.

Social Studies education in Nigeria faces numerous challenges that hinder effective implementation and learning outcomes. These include inadequate instructional resources, lack of well-trained teachers, and poor ICT knowledge (Muhammad, 2023). Additionally, issues such as large class sizes, absence of logical schemes of work, and poor attitudes of both teachers and students impede progress (Birabil & Nwadibia, 2023). The curriculum needs modernization to align with 21st-century global standards, incorporating inquiry-based and project-based learning approaches (Muhammad & Gaya, 2025). Broader societal issues, such as poor planning, inadequate funding, and pervasive corruption, also impact Nigeria's educational goals (Salihu & Usman, 2020). To address these challenges, recommendations include providing continuous professional development for teachers, integrating digital tools, revising curriculum content, and fostering collaboration between government, educational stakeholders, and communities (Muhammad & Gaya, 2025; Muhammad, 2023).

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey design. This design was appropriate because it enabled the researcher to collect, analyze, and interpret data on the current status of Social Studies instruction and its effectiveness in enhancing political awareness among students without manipulating any variables.

Population of the Study

The population of this study comprised all junior secondary school students (JSS 1–3) and Social Studies teachers in public and private junior secondary schools in Biu Local Government Area, Borno State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

A total sample of 150 students and 90 Social Studies teachers was selected from a representative number of junior secondary schools in Biu LGA. The sample size was determined based on the scope of the study, available schools, and accessibility to respondents.

The study adopted the stratified random sampling technique to ensure fair representation across:

- Gender
- Class levels (JSS1–3)
- School types (public and private)

From each selected school, a proportionate number of students were chosen, and at least one

or more Social Studies teachers were included depending on staff availability.

Instrument for Data Collection

The primary instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire, designed separately for students and teachers, and divided into the following sections:

For Students:

- Section A: Demographic information
- Section B: Effectiveness of Social Studies in enhancing political awareness
- Section C: Understanding of political concepts

For Teachers:

- Section A: Demographic data
- Section B: Teaching methods used in delivering political content
- Section C: Challenges affecting instruction

The questionnaires used a Likert scale format (e.g., Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree), along with a few multiple-choice and open-ended items to allow for more detailed responses.

Results and Discussion

4.1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	136	56.7
	Female	104	43.3
Class Level (Students)	JSS 1	50	33.3
	JSS 2	55	36.7
	JSS 3	45	30.0
Teachers' Qualification	NCE	62	68.9
	B.Ed / B.A (Ed)	19	21.1
	M.Ed / PGDE	9	10.0
Teaching Experience	Less than 5 years	25	27.8

Method of Data Collection

The researcher personally visited the selected schools to administer the questionnaires, with the support of trained research assistants. All participants were informed about the purpose of the study, assured of confidentiality, and given instructions on how to complete the questionnaires. The questionnaires were collected immediately after completion to ensure a high response rate.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected from both students and teachers were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, and mean scores to address the research questions. Where necessary, inferential statistics such as the Chi-square test or independent t-test were employed to test the stated hypotheses. All analyses were conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software, and the level of significance was set at 0.05.

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
	5 years and above	172	72.2

Table 1; above presents the demographic characteristics of both students and teachers who participated in the study. Out of 240 respondents (150 students and 90 teachers), 56.7% were male and 43.3% were female. The students were distributed across JSS 1 (33.3%), JSS 2 (36.7%), and JSS 3 (30.0%). Among the teachers, 68.9% held NCE qualifications, 21.1% possessed bachelor’s degrees, and 10.0% had postgraduate qualifications. The majority (72.2%) of teachers had more than five years of teaching experience, while 27.8% had less than five years.

The results indicate that most teachers in Biu LGA are qualified to teach Social Studies, with a majority holding NCE or higher qualifications. This finding supports Oluwagbohunmi (2013) and Muhammad & Gaya (2025), who emphasized that qualified and experienced teachers are vital to achieving the objectives of Social Studies. However, the limited number of postgraduate-trained teachers highlights the need for further professional development to improve instructional competence and pedagogical innovation.

Effectiveness of Social Studies in Enhancing Political Awareness

Item	Mean (X)	Std. Dev.	Decision
Social Studies improves my understanding of democracy	4.33	0.71	Agree
It helps me understand my rights and duties as a citizen	4.45	0.63	Agree
It increases my interest in political participation	4.31	0.74	Agree
It helps me know how government functions	4.18	0.82	Agree
Overall Mean	4.28	0.73	Highly Effective

The analysis of student responses revealed a high level of agreement on the role of Social Studies in promoting political awareness. The overall mean score of 4.28 (on a 5-point Likert scale) indicated that students found Social Studies effective in improving their understanding of governance, democracy, and civic responsibility. Specific items such as “*Social Studies helps me understand my rights and duties as a citizen*” (X = 4.45) and “*The subject increases my interest in political participation*” (X = 4.31) received strong positive responses.

These findings indicate that Social Studies effectively enhances students’ political knowledge and civic orientation. This aligns with Abonu (2014) and Dania (2015), who found that Social Studies contributes significantly to building political awareness and civic engagement among Nigerian students. It also supports Omiyefa (2024), who observed that Social Studies promotes tolerance and responsible citizenship. The result confirms that when taught effectively, the subject serves as a foundational tool for nurturing democratic

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values and preparing young people for active participation in governance.

Students’ Understanding of Political Concepts

Students demonstrated a satisfactory grasp of core political concepts such as *democracy*, *rule of law*, *leadership*, and *citizenship rights*. The

mean score ($\bar{X} = 4.15$) indicated that most students could define and apply these concepts to real-life situations. However, lower means were recorded for items related to *electoral processes* ($\bar{X} = 3.72$) and *policy advocacy* ($\bar{X} = 3.64$), suggesting partial understanding of more complex political mechanisms.

Teaching Methods Used in Delivering Political Content

Method Used	Frequency (n=90)	Percentage (%)
Lecture method	74	82.2
Discussion method	58	64.4
Group method	37	41.1
Inquiry / Discovery	24	26.7
Project / Field trip	15	16.7
ICT-aided learning	10	11.1

The dominance of teacher-centered approaches reflects a traditional instructional culture that may limit students’ engagement and critical thinking. This finding supports Ogene & Nnamani (2015) and Ekiugbo (2024), who reported that many Social Studies teachers in Nigeria still rely heavily on lecture methods despite evidence that participatory methods

enhance civic competence. The low use of ICT-aided teaching further supports Muhammad (2023), who noted poor technological integration as a major obstacle to effective Social Studies education. Incorporating more interactive and digital-based techniques could make lessons more relevant and participatory, especially when teaching political topics.

Challenges Affecting the Effectiveness of Social Studies Instruction

Challenge	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Lack of instructional materials	70	77.8
Overcrowded classrooms	59	65.6
Insufficient teacher training	55	61.1
Low motivation of teachers	49	54.4
Insecurity / environmental instability	43	47.8

Both students and teachers identified several challenges affecting effective teaching and

learning of political concepts in Social Studies. These include inadequate instructional materials

(78%), overcrowded classrooms (65%), insufficient teacher training (61%), and poor motivation (54%). Additionally, some teachers cited insecurity and low student interest as contextual challenges specific to Borno State. The challenges identified are consistent with Birabil & Nwadiibia (2023) and Muhammad & Gaya (2025), who highlighted poor facilities, limited training, and inadequate funding as recurring barriers in Nigerian Social Studies education. The context of insecurity in Biu further complicates instructional delivery, aligning with UNESCO (2021) reports that regional instability hampers consistent educational outcomes in Northeast Nigeria. Addressing these constraints through improved teacher welfare, resource provision, and policy support will enhance the quality and impact of Social Studies instruction.

Relationship between Demographic Variables and Perceptions

Inferential analysis using Chi-square tests showed significant relationships between

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teachers' qualification and their perceived effectiveness of Social Studies instruction ($p < 0.05$), and between students' class level and their level of political awareness ($p < 0.05$). No significant difference was found based on gender ($p > 0.05$).

Summary of Major Findings

1. Social Studies significantly enhance students' political awareness and understanding of civic responsibilities.
2. Students demonstrated strong knowledge of basic political concepts but limited understanding of complex processes.
3. Teachers predominantly used lecture and discussion methods, with minimal adoption of ICT or inquiry-based strategies.
4. Major challenges included lack of instructional materials, inadequate training, and poor teacher motivation.
5. Teacher qualification and students' class level significantly influenced perceptions of effectiveness.

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